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Труды научно-технической конференции "Новые технологии и научно-технические достижения промышленности - человеку, обществу, государству" - ПРОМТЕХЭКСПО XXI

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Digital magnetic variation station «QUARTZ-4»

The creation of a uniform network of magnetic observatories (*MO*) in territory of Russia with the uniform centre of coordination and operative access to the data is necessary for the decision of scientific and applied tasks of terrestrial magnetism at their sharing with the data of a global network *MO* and data of manetometrical satellite shootings. The study of a magnetic field on the data of ground and satellite supervision is necessary for the decision of fundamental problems: 1) *physics*, - generation of magnetic fields in a nature; 2) *geophysics*, - study of a structure and processes in deep bowels of the Earth; 3) *solar-terrestrial physics*, - study of influence of the solar geoeffective phenomena on magnetosphere and ionosphere of the Earth; 4) *geology*, - study of a litosphere structure of the Earth on the data of an abnormal magnetic field and of an electrical inductional currents in the Earth crust.

There is a lot of applied tasks solved with the help of the data on spatial structure and variations of a geomagnetic field. It, first of all, task of navigation, task of allocation of abnormal fields for the purposes of geological prospecting, task of an estimation of influence on technical systems, including satellite, task of influence on biosystems, forecast of geomagnetic activity.

In connection with the discussed international scientific projects (International Geophysical Year, International Gelio-georhysical Year, International Polar Year and Electronic Geophysical Year) the problem of reorganization of system geomagnetic observatories of Russia has got the special urgency. The out-of-date equipment, graphic record, absence of telemetry make to impossible inclusion Russian *MO* in a global network and deprive the Russian and world scientific public of a practical opportunity of the scientific analysis of the geomagnetic data in all Russian longitude sector. By way of preparation and realizations of the specified International projects the conducting institutes of Russia should undertake the certain efforts on modernization of a Russian *MO* network.

IZMIRAN is sole organization in Russia developing and making the precision equipment on the basis of quartz magnetic sensors (*QMS*) for registration and research of geomagnetic variations. With this equipment are equipped all MO of Russia and many foreign observatories. The presence of the qualified experts and possessed experience, allows to carry out further perfection of modern quartz variation stations being a MO basis, on the basis of development *Bobrov-Burtsev-Belov*, which, as the wide experience of their operation on a number of Russia observatories and abroad has shown, are successfully used in the international programs, switching INTERMAGNET (observatories «Irkutsk», «Beijing», «Sodankuly», «Tichan»). One of last development in the field of creation of devices of new generation for MO on a QMS basis is the digital magnetic variation station (*DMVS*) «QUARTZ-4».

DMVS «QUARTZ-4», is intended for continuous measurement and registration in a digital kind of a vector of the Earth magnetic field (*VEMF*) component variations on a network Russian MO, and also in conditions unattended (*UT*) or seldom served (*SS*) of items of supervision. DMVS «QUARTZ-4» measures and accumulates in solid-state memory in a digital kind of three components VEMF variations importance and of temperature meaning of quartz magnetic measuring converters (*MMC*) in real time.

DMVS «QUARTZ-4» can be applied in forwarding conditions at realization of complex geophysical measurements and geological researches. At use of the device in field forwarding conditions, in UT or SS conditions of items of supervision the tax saved by the device (*MMC* of the device) data by the operator is stipulated through the special control panel (*SCP*) on the consecutive channel of connection with their subsequent swapping in the computer.

The nearest analogue «QUARTZ-4» is the domestic device DMVS «QUARTZ-3EM», developed in IZMIRAN [1, 2], which for more than ten years' term of operation in the different countries has shown high metrological characteristics satisfying to the modern requirements on accuracy and stability of the indications. Development and application of special optical system of the photo-electric converter of angular displacement in a design of variation station «QUARTZ-3EM» have allowed maximum to realize all advantages of a quartz magnetosensitivity element, and, besides it is essential to increase a range up to 5000 nT and to improve resolution up to 0,1 nT, and also to expand frequency the characteristics up to 15 Hz. In result these variation stations have found wide application as in Russia, and abroad. For example, the zone of polar lights is wholly blocked by these stations from cape Welen in extreme east up to Sodankuly in Finland. In Antarctic Continent 7 stations, from them two on Chinese observatories «Zong Shan» and «Great Wall», two stations on «Mirny» observatory, one - on «Novolazarevskaya» observatory and two stations on observatory «Vostok» successfully work. And on «Vostok» observatory these DMVS were shared with the American scientists from Michigan University within the framework of the joint project «Research of the high latitudinal geomagnetic phenomena». DMVS «QUARTZ-3EM» has passed presentation and metrological checking in Hungary (1990), in China and Finland (1991) and in France (1992) [3].

Distinctive feature DMVS «QUARTZ-4» is that it is high stable, intellectual device of new generation with ample opportunities of program installation and change of various parameters of the circuit, opportunity of digital processing and filtration of the measurements, given during realization, opportunity of integration in the international system of data gathering *INTERMAGNET*.

The base complete set DMVS consists of the following basic units: the block of sensors (*BS*), adjusting platform (*AP*), block of electronics (*BE*), special control panel (*SCP*), block of measurement and accumulation of the information (*BMA*), power unit (*PU*), protective casing (*PC*) or container (*CO*) and complete set of connecting cables. BS includes three variometers, consisting from QMS D, H, Z with graduate by rings, coils of a feedback, photo converters and elements of exact adjustment on a magnetic field in a point of measurements, and also temperature sensor. AP contains elements of fastening QMS, liquid levels and elements of a platform adjusting.

BE includes an analog amplifiers, controller, analog-digital converter (*ADC*), serial port RS-232/485 and power supply. BE provides transfer of the data and information interchange with SCP (or BMA) on distance up to 3 ... 5 m, has maximum unmagnetic performance and settles down in immediate proximity from BS.

BMA contains microcontroller, timer, memory of the data and programs, graphic indicator, interface and power supply. On the graphic display of BMA the opportunity of a conclusion (demonstration) of the diagrams of measuring variations of VEMF in real time, conclusion of the diagram of measured temperature of an environment and construction three-hour *K-index* magnetic activity is stipulated. The opportunity of viewing on the display of the diagrams given before written down in memory of the device, opportunity of scaling measuring data on a temporary and peak scale, opportunity of an every measuring channel registration of the data with the maximal resolution MMC, and also opportunity of visualization of process of filling of memory of the device and control of a voltage of the power supply is stipulated. The accumulation of the data in BMA or personal computer in a continuous mode in MO conditions is stipulated through the consecutive channel of connection with speed not less than 9600 Bod. The timer managing work DMVS, has the channel of synchronization with GPS and opportunity of correction of a course of hours of real time. At use of the device in MO conditions the opportunity of escalating of system is stipulated by increase of number of measuring channels (for example, connection proton magnetometer, inclination device or other sensors).

SCP is executed as the compact (portable) device of the minimal sizes and weight, which electro feeding is carried out from the built - in independent power supply, and includes a micro controller (controller, serial port RS-232), timer, memory of the data and programs, and also digital indicator. The size of the built - in non-volatile memory provides of the information output consistently and simultaneously from 3 ... 4 DMVS, working in a UT mode is independent.

The software provides organization of a database DMVS, opportunity of data processing for use them in a format, suitable for participation in the program *INTERMAGNET*. The software provides organization on DMVS

«QUARTZ-4» base of system of the tax of the information by connection of additional measuring channels through the consecutive channel of communication.

Three basic variants of performance of the device shown in the Table are stipulated.

Variant of performance	Using	Components of a product						
		MMC	BMA	PU	SCP	Casing	Cable	Manual
«QUARTZ-4»	MO	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
«QUARTZ-4-01»	SS	+	+	+	-	PC	+	+
«QUARTZ-4-02»	UT	+	-	+	+	CO	+	+

The circuit of MMC construction for all variants of DMVS «QUARTZ-4» performance is identical functionally in completed unit and includes functional blocks: BS, AP (not demonstrate in *figure*) and BE. The MMC design, variants, specified in the *Table*, of performance of the device, is defined by conditions of its application. In *figure* the block diagrams of two possible variants of MO construction on DMVS «QUARTZ-4» base are submitted.

Block-scheme of magnetic observatory on the base of DAMS "QUARTZ-4"

The AP design provides mutual orthogonality of QMS basic vectors to within 1 angular minute and rigid fixing rather each other. Variometers have the optical adaptation for QMS visual installation in relation to a direction of a VEMF horizontal component with an error no more than **5 angular minutes** and liquid level with the accuracy of **1 angular minute**. The temperature sensor established on AP has unmagnetic performance and thermal contact to the Z-variometer case.

Block-scheme of magnetic observatory on the base of DAMS "QUARTZ-4" and proton magnetometer

All metal parts of BS, BE and SCP (BMA) of the device are made of unmagnetic materials, the connecting cables have water-resistant isolation.

DMVS «QUARTZ-4» is intended for continuous round-the-clock work in field conditions or in MO conditions, with BS and AP installation on unmagnetic pedestal of variation pavilion.

MMC in variant for SS performance has a protective casing from a unmagnetic material, on which cover the "bench-mark" line " for a binding of the block on azimuthal direction is designated. The MMC in UT variant of performance is established in the unmagnetic tight container, on which case the adaptations for orientation of a vertical axis of the container concerning a plane of a magnetic meridian are established. On the case of the container the tight socket for SCP connection is located. At work in UT conditions tight container with MMC it is supposed to dig in vertically in ground on depth more than 1 m, thus use elongate cable with hermetic socket for connection of the independent power supply and SCP is stipulated.

The circuit of construction of station provides its serviceability in field conditions (UT) at temperature of an air in limits from a minus 30 up to +40°C. At work in conditions of an unmagnetic pavilion, for maintenance of high stability of measurements, temperature of an environment should be supported at a level (15±5)°C at incidental fluctuations in limits from 5 up to 30°C . At work in MO conditions temperature of an environment should be supported at a level (20±0,5)°C , the humidity of air should be supported in this case in limits from 55 up to 85%.

The basic characteristics of DAMS «QUARTZ-4»

Measuring components of VEMF	D, H, Z
Measuring dynamic range of variations on each component of VEMF	± 2000 nT (is scaled by programm)
Frequency of data digitasing of variations	from 0 up to 100 Hz
Sensitivity on each of measuring channels	0,1 nT
Sensitivity of the temperature measurement channel	0,1°C
Cycle of automatic measurements	0,1 ... 3600 s (is established by programm)

Sensitivity to leveling of sensors, no more	1,5 nT/angular degree
The basic systematic error of measurements, no more	± 1 nT
Long-term instability zero - item in magnetic observatory conditions	0,25 nT/months
Range of working temperatures	from a minus 30 up to + 40°C
Temperature factor everyone of variometers, no more	$\pm 0,5$ nT/°C
Capacity of non-volatile memory of the data, not less	16 Mb
Voltage from a source of a constant current	12 ± 3 V
Consumed capacity, no more	5 W
Term of independent work of the device in UT mode with a 60 s cycle of measurement, not less	180 days

Offered IZMIRAN today the technical decisions on equipment the MO modern DMVS and new intellectual devices (with system of remote control by process of measurements and transfer of the information), will allow considerably to automate process of measurement, to simplify reception of the demanded scientific data and will allow essentially to reduce expenses by construction of special pavilions, and also to reduce number of the personnel, serving them, that will result in economy of means.

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Вы 4-й посетитель данной статьи.

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